

APECS

Association of Polar
Early Career Scientists

2016-2020 Strategic Plan

APECS Mission and Strategic Aim

The goals of APECS include creating opportunities for the development of innovative, international, and interdisciplinary collaborations among current early career polar researchers as well as recruiting, retaining, and promoting the next generation of polar enthusiasts.

Specifically we aim to:

- Maintain a network of polar researchers across disciplines and national boundaries to meet, share ideas and experiences, and develop new research directions and collaborations.
- Offer opportunities for career development towards both traditional and alternative professions related to the polar regions and the cryosphere.
- Promote education and outreach as an integral component of polar research.

APECS Strategic Plan

The **Association of Polar Early Career Scientists (APECS)** is an international and interdisciplinary organization for undergraduate and graduate students, postdoctoral researchers, early career professionals, early career faculty members, educators and others interested in the Polar and Alpine regions and the wider cryosphere. It provides a platform for promoting collaborations and exchange among its members and with the wider Polar research community, endeavouring to create a continuum of leadership in polar sciences.

APECS recognizes the importance of fostering the next generation of researchers who will be faced with responding to the increasingly critical challenges in the Polar regions resulting from the impacts of climate change.

Since its inception during the International Polar Year (IPY) in 2007-2008, APECS continues to provide networking and career development opportunities for early career scientists by working with many international partners in the Polar research community. It also continues to promote education and outreach as integral components of polar research. The organization maintains rapid growth, both in membership and geographically, with the quantity of activities and projects led by APECS members increasing accordingly.

APECS has proven successful in building on extensive international, national and interdisciplinary networks to develop integrated research directions, meet career development needs, and communicate the urgencies of polar science to a worldwide audience.

This APECS Strategic Plan 2016 - 2020 addresses both the challenges, as identified by the Organizational Review, and opportunities for APECS through five main Strategic Goals:

Goal 1: CAPACITY BUILDING. Engage in partnerships at local, national, regional, and international scales to ensure that APECS continues to bring leadership opportunities to early career researchers (ECRs) and to make meaningful contributions within the Polar community.

Goal 2: CUTTING EDGE OF INFORMATION ASSESSMENT. Maintain and increase the diversity of APECS online and in-person resources and activities focusing on academic and non-academic career paths, research education and outreach, and ensure their effective delivery to APECS members and to non-APECS communities.

Goal 3: OUTREACH. Increase communication through an improved internal communication flow, improved online communication, the creation of a social media strategy and the maintenance of regular communication with APECS partners and the wider Polar community.

Goal 4: ESTABLISH A STRUCTURE TO GROW SUSTAINABLY. Improve the knowledge transfer within and between all levels of the organization to achieve better project management, more integrated communication with APECS national committees and improve membership diversity

Goal 5: IMPROVE INTERNAL FUNCTIONS. Ensure sustainable funding for APECS core operations (International Directorate), activities and projects, and continue to work with APECS partners to develop funding support for early career researchers and to provide training opportunities for early career researchers to develop the skills to obtain funding for their research and career development.

This new Strategic Plan provides a framework to guide APECS actions in providing opportunities for early career scientists and fostering a continuum of leadership in polar sciences.

Goal 1: Capacity Building

In order to ensure that APECS continues to bring leadership opportunities to early career researchers (ECRs) and make meaningful contributions within the Polar community, APECS engages in partnerships with other polar organizations at the national, regional, and international scales. Such partnerships have been established and are fostered at all levels (affiliations, formal agreements, and informal relations), in order to stimulate and develop shared initiatives that are meaningful to ECRs whilst leveraging resources.

Actions:

Increase the number of leadership opportunities available to ECRs in partner organizations. Increasingly, partner organizations are asking APECS to nominate or recommend ECRs to serve on working groups and steering committees. So far, partner organizations have been very satisfied with early career representatives on their committees, and ECRs have reported that these opportunities provide valuable career experience and networking opportunities for APECS members. APECS will work in concert with partner organizations to create these opportunities. Increased effort will also be made to publicize activities undertaken with partner organizations to the APECS membership so that more ECRs are aware of and appreciate the value of said partnerships.

Goal 1: Capacity Building

Expand APECS partnerships both with national and international level organizations and institutions. As APECS grows, the national committees are taking on a more prominent role opening opportunities to promote and formalize partnerships with organizations and institutions in those countries. APECS must clarify what it offers to partners as well as benefits it may obtain from joint projects.

Explore partnerships with indigenous organizations. APECS members recognize that the social dimensions of polar research are often not integrated with the work of physical scientists and have, therefore, identified increasing outreach activities and membership in northern and indigenous communities as a priority. Increasing the number and strength of collaborations with indigenous community organizations is a way to get in touch with ECRs in remote communities, and to better understand what resources we can offer to these communities.

Continue to engage in politically neutral partnerships. APECS is committed to providing a neutral platform for ECRs engaged in polar and alpine research, not advocating for any particular point of view. Clear guidelines must be established explaining what APECS considers to be advocacy, and these guidelines should be made known to APECS leadership and National Committees.

APECS World Summit 2015

The first Association of Polar Early Career Scientists (APECS) World Summit, “The Future of Polar Research” was convened in Sofia, Bulgaria from 6-8 June 2015, before an audience of 76 participants from 25 countries including representatives from 20 APECS National Committees (NCs) and mentors from 12 organizations. The Summit included an icebreaker, and workshops on both open data in polar research and the future of polar research and of APECS itself. Outcomes of the Summit included agreement on the importance of open data for research progress in the Polar Regions and fortification of the APECS network itself through continued sharing of information within the APECS community. The second World Summit is planned at the 2018 SCAR / IASC Conference in Davos Switzerland in 2018.

Goal 2: Cutting Edge of Information Assessment

APECS is a member-driven organization, and its resources and activities are created for the members by the members, as well as for our partners and the public. Three main themes encompass APECS' resources and activities: Research, Education and Outreach (E&O), and Career Development. APECS strives to maintain and increase the diversity of APECS online and in-person resources and activities, focusing on academic and non-academic career paths, research, E&O, and to ensure their effective delivery to APECS members and to non-APECS communities.

Online Resources and Activities

The APECS website hosts a wealth of information resources spanning the research, E&O, and career development themes (Table 3.1). The website is a key tool to transfer knowledge to members. APECS also hosts online events, including conferences and webinars, that serve as both knowledge sharing platforms.

In-Person Events

With membership spread worldwide, APECS in-person events are often tied to conferences that members will already be attending. In-person events are used as a catalyst for networking, career development, and motivation to strengthen membership involvement. These events provide ideal opportunities to connect, learn, and share experiences, information, and knowledge. Examples of APECS organized in-person events can be found in Table 1.

Actions:

Maintain online activities, keeping them up-to-date and meaningful, while continuing to explore new approaches. APECS will continue to offer online programs,

Goal 2: Information Assessment

Resource or Activity	Description	Type
Webinars	Themed talks by experts, with open discussion	E&O, Research and Career Development, online
FrostBytes	Short video clips of research highlights prepared by members	Research and E&O, online
Field School Database	Curated list of intensive training courses offered around the world	Research and Career Development, online
Event Calendar	List of Polar related conferences and workshops	E&O, Research, online
Polar Outreach Catalogue	Web-based list of Education, Outreach, and Communication projects occurring during the 2007-2008 International Polar Year	E&O, online
APECS Publication Database	List of publications from APECS projects and initiatives	E&O, research, online
Jobs Database	Curated list of open positions of interest to the APECS community	Career Development, online
Graduate Programmes Database	Curated list of polar-related graduate programs around the world	Career development, online
Mentor Panels	Dialogue with experienced researchers	Career Development, in person
Workshops	Interactive, educational experiences	Career Development, research, in person
Icebreakers and pub nights	Social events designed to facilitate networking and dialogue	Career Development, in person

Table 1: Examples of APECS resources and activities and the type of niche each fills.

Goal 2: Information Assessment

and is experimenting with different online platforms to engage ECRs. Webinars have been very successful in the past but are not the sole means for online learning. Online events should be offered with an interdisciplinary focus, and members should be asked for input regarding topics. Website resources should be carefully curated, and archived as appropriate in order to maintain an approachable repository for information.

Increase opportunities for in-person events. The APECS membership recognizes the value of in-person events, and so does the organization as a whole. APECS will continue to work closely with members who are attending conferences to help provide networking activities or organize mentor panels and smaller workshops at meetings. The APECS leadership will continue to search for funding opportunities that allow for the organization of larger workshops or stand-alone APECS in person events.

Encourage publications and presentation to ensure knowledge transfer to a broader audience. APECS members are always looking for ways to collaborate with one another and with mentors. APECS will continue to work closely with these members and encourage them to publish and present at conferences the results of APECS projects, meetings, and events.

Develop resources for non-academic career paths. Not all graduates from polar-related programs can or want to continue in an academic career. Providing information about potential career types, necessary skills, potential employers will be an important area of focus for APECS in the coming years.

IPY Education, Outreach and Communication (EOC) Assessment

One of the results of the 2007-2009 International Polar Year (IPY) was an unprecedented, worldwide effort in polar education, outreach, and communication (EOC) projects. As a joint project between APECS, the International Arctic Science Committee (IASC) and the Scientific Committee on Antarctic Research (SCAR), and funded by the International Council for Science (ICSU), the IPY EOC Assessment catalogued over 550 IPY EOC activities that were created in more than 25 languages from 70 countries around the globe. The IPY Outreach Assessment led to multiple presentations at international conferences, along with the development of the Polar Outreach Catalogue, all of which now comprise some of APECS valuable online resources.

Goal 3: Outreach

Effective communication is a critical tool for engaging with members, coordinating projects, ensuring strong leadership, and building a durable and active APECS community. The organization will increase coordination and interaction through improved internal communication flow and online communication, the creation of a social media strategy, and the maintenance of regular communication with APECS partners and the wider Polar community.

Actions:

Improve online communications and create a social media strategy. Because APECS members live in geographically diverse regions, online communication is key to facilitating projects and maintaining member engagement. It is important to maintain an ongoing, coherent presence across a range of online platforms: at present the APECS website, eNewsletter, online meeting platforms (e.g., GoToMeeting), and social media are all tools that are in use. Creating a social media strategy that is reviewed annually by the ExCom will help ensure that the APECS online presence remains relevant, neutral and responds to the needs of members.

Build bridges with the wider polar community. Maintaining regular communication with APECS partners and the wider polar community is vital to the ongoing success

Goal 3: Outreach

of the organization. Opening and consolidating communication channels with indigenous people, polar and scientific organizations, policy makers, schools, and non-polar scientists is a priority. This will be achieved through networking at in-person meetings, creating an inclusive structure for spreading APECS news, and by making formal approaches to potential partners. Such connections can then be formalized, helping to cement the role of APECS in the polar research landscape. Developing and promoting the APECS mentor programme will help facilitate communication between members and mentors on a personal level, as it offers a supportive route for first contact.

Goal 4: Establish a Structure to Grow Sustainably

All APECS activities are governed by the organizational Terms of Reference and Rules of Procedure which are updated in response to the needs of this dynamic organization. Figure 1 depicts the structure as of October 2015. We aim to improve the knowledge transfer within and between all levels of the organization to achieve better project management, more integrated communication and improve membership diversity.

Figure 1: The organizational structure of APECS. The various positions are described in more detail below. The lines represents the flow of positions and knowledge transfer among various parts of the organization. The boxes not connected are elected or selected through various channels and not necessarily APECS members.

Goal 4: Structure for Growth

International Directorate: The International Directorate is the secretariat of APECS serving as the main contact point for members and partners, providing support for APECS activities, projects, and committees while also providing continuity and institutional memory. It currently includes one full-time position (Executive Director) funded from 2009 through 2016 by the Research Council of Norway, UiT The Arctic University of Norway and the Norwegian Polar Institute.

Executive Committee: The 5-member Executive Committee (ExCom) is elected annually by the Council. One of them serves as APECS President, the remainder as APECS Vice-Presidents for their term. The committee maintains core activities, implements new initiatives and ensures information exchange. It is supported by the International Directorate as well as past-Presidents and past-ExCom members who may remain on the ExCom in an ex-officio, non-voting role.

Council: The APECS Council is composed of individual members who are self-nominated and approved by the Executive Committee. APECS National Committees and early career partner organizations may also nominate a representative to the Council. The Council is lead by two co-chairs. The work on the Council is organized in Project Groups that are lead by Council members but are also open for participation for non-Council APECS members.

Project Groups: Project Groups consist of 3-10 individuals cooperating on a clearly defined project (e.g. mentorship award, Polar Week, webinar series).

National Committees (NCs): The APECS National Committees represent the regional branches of the larger international organization. The structure of NCs is flexible, some

Figure 2: Countries of residence for APECS members are highlighted in blue.

Goal 4: Structure for Growth

being committees within APECS while others are registered as independent organizations in their country but affiliated with APECS and recognized as an APECS National Committee.

General Members: Membership is open to anyone with an interest in the Polar and Alpine Regions and the wider Cryosphere and is free (with the option of a voluntary donation).

Advisory Committee: The APECS Advisory Committee comprises senior-level polar researchers and professionals. This Committee provides advice and support for the APECS leadership to help steer the direction of APECS and ensure its sustainability.

APECS Representatives: APECS representatives are ECRs that represent APECS at meetings, and on committees and projects of partner organisations. They are open and advertised to APECS members and provide a training opportunity for our members to network and gain experience in a wide range of skills.

Actions:

Implement an internal communication workflow. To facilitate internal exchange of information, Project Groups and National Committees will have standard interim report forms that will allow the APECS leadership to better follow through on project developments.

Continue to increase the transparency of APECS Representative selection process. Maintain diversity of APECS Representatives and establish clear guidelines for both the election of representatives and the work of those representatives once elected.

Closer integration of the National Committees (NCs). The NCs are crucial to the success of APECS as they are often the first point of contact for members and local organizations. Partnership agreements will be established for all active NCs to standardize the relationships between APECS and the NCs. Under the new agreements each NC will nominate a representative to sit on the Council, facilitating information exchange (Fig. 1).

Improve project management. In order to enhance the effectiveness and oversight of APECS' activities, all ongoing and completed projects will be registered in a database. APECS will regularly evaluate its projects in order to direct resources where they are most needed.

Expanding membership diversity. APECS will strive to diversify its membership base across disciplines, countries and career level.

Goal 5: Improve Internal Functions

As a not-for-profit organization APECS must ensure sustainable funding for core operations (International Directorate), activities and projects, and continue to work with APECS partners to develop funding support for ECRs, and to provide training opportunities for early career researchers to develop the skills to find funding for their research and career development.

Since 2009 the APECS International Directorate has consisted of one full-time staff member, the Executive Director, located in Tromsø, Norway. The Directorate is funded until the end of 2016 by the Research Council of Norway, the UiT The Arctic University of Norway and the Norwegian Polar Institute.

Actions:

Maintaining the APECS International Directorate. APECS will continue to seek funding to maintain its International Directorate with a minimum of one full-time staff (Executive Director) serving as the main contact point for members and partners, providing support for APECS activities / projects / committees and also providing continuity and organizational memory. Securing funding for a second position in the International Directorate will be a priority to fully support the growing organization and its needs. APECS will work with its international partners and apply for project funding to ensure the continuation of its Directorate in the future.

Goal 5: Improve Internal Functions

Funding support for early career researchers. APECS will continue to work with its partners to develop funding support opportunities for early career researchers for events (e.g. travel support to conferences) and early career representation in international projects and committees. APECS will also continue at times and when available to administer dedicated early career funds and / or their distribution on behalf of its international partners.

Funding support for APECS projects. APECS will continue to fundraise for its activities by applying for available grants from funding agencies and international organizations. With the growth and formalization of the APECS NCs, APECS will work with the NCs to access national funding sources in their home countries. Support from APECS funds will continue to be provided for projects, committees and representatives if available and with clear and transparent procedures.

Exploring additional funding sources. APECS will expand its efforts to explore additional income sources for the organization. These efforts can include, but are not limited to, more actively encouraging donations from members and partners and exploring private sector funding sources under the terms of the APECS donations policy.

Background

The Strategic Plan outlined herein is the result of discussions among the APECS leadership (Executive Committee, Council, and APECS Directorate), the APECS National Committees, and extensive consultation with the wider APECS membership and polar research community. The community was consulted in three main ways:

APECS Organizational Review 2015: The review was led by a committee comprised of APECS members and mentors to assess both the efficiency of current activities of APECS and to advise on the future direction of the organization. The review consisted of informal feedback opportunities as well as a comprehensive survey. The survey received over 200 responses from 29 different countries. The final recommendations of the APECS Organisational Review 2015 were published in September 2015 (see attachment).

APECS World Summit 2015: The summit was held in Sofia, Bulgaria in June 2015 and brought together representatives of the APECS leadership and National Committees.

Consultation among APECS Council and National Committees: A wider consultation in the form of a survey among the APECS leadership and National Committees was conducted in June / July 2015. The survey allowed comments on the recommendations of the APECS Organisational Review as well as recommendations and ideas for their implementation.

The APECS Strategic Plan 2016 - 2020 was written by the 2014-2015 and 2015-2016 APECS Executive Committees, with the help of the International Directorate and the APECS Council.

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